

SYNTHESIS OF COUMARINS FROM O-HYDROXYBENZOPHENONES

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5-Methyl-, 5-chloro-, 3-chloro-5-methyl-2-methoxybenzophenones have been condensed with ethyl bromoacetate and ethyl α -bromopropionate under Reformatsky's condition to yield hydroxy esters which have been dehydrated to the unsaturated esters and the latter on demethylation give quantitative yields of coumarin derivatives.

In continuation of the work of Chakravarti *et al* (Chakravarti and Mazumdar, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1938, 15, 136; Chakravarti and Dutta, *ibid.*, 1940, 17, 65; Chakravarti and Bera, *ibid.*, 1944, 21, 44) on the synthesis of coumarin derivatives from *o*-hydroxy-aryl-alkyl ketones it has been found that the *o*-hydroxybenzophenones also give good yields of coumarin derivatives.

The ketones *e.g.*, 2-methoxy-5-methyl-, 2-methoxy-5-chloro- and 2-methoxy-3-chloro-5-methylbenzophenones have been condensed with ethyl bromoacetate and with ethyl α -bromopropionate forming hydroxy-esters, which have been treated with thionyl chloride and pyridine to yield unsaturated esters. These unsaturated esters on being treated with hydriodic acid yield coumarins quantitatively.

Ketones used.	Halogenated fatty ester	Coumarins obtained.
2-Methoxy-5-methylbenzophenone	Ethyl bromoacetate	4-Phenyl-6-methylcoumarin
2-Methoxy-5-chlorobenzophenone	Ethyl bromoacetate	4-Phenyl-6-chlorocoumarin
"	Ethyl α -bromopropionate	3-Methyl-4-phenyl-6-chlorocoumarin
2-Methoxy-3-chloro-5-methylbenzophenone	Ethyl bromoacetate	4-Phenyl-6-methyl-8-chlorocoumarin
"	Ethyl α -bromopropionate	3:6-Dimethyl-4-phenyl-8-chlorocoumarin

EXPERIMENTAL

Preparation of 4-Phenyl-6-methylcoumarin from 2-Hydroxy-5-methylbenzophenone

2-Hydroxy-5-methylbenzophenone.—The benzoate of *p*-cresol (26 g.) was mixed with finely powdered anhydrous aluminium chloride (30 g.) and the mixture heated at 130-40° in the absence of moisture for 1 hour. The glassy mass was decomposed with ice-cold dilute hydrochloric acid, when the product solidified and it was crystallised from dilute alcohol as yellow needles, m.p. 87°, yield 23 g. It is identical with the compound prepared by Rosenmünd and Schnürr (*Annalen*, 1927, 460, 84). *2-Methoxy-5-methylbenzophenone* was obtained by the methylation of the above compound with dimethyl sulphate in the usual manner. The oil obtained was taken up with ether, the ethereal extract washed with water and dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. It distilled at 190°/4 mm. as a yellow oil. (Found: C, 79.58; H, 6.20. $C_{15}H_{14}O_2$ requires C, 79.65; H, 6.19 per cent).

4-Phenyl-6-methylcoumarin.—Ethyl 2-methoxy-5-methyl- β -phenylcinnamate, prepared by the reaction of 2-methoxy-5-methylbenzophenone and ethyl bromoacetate in the presence of zinc wool and the subsequent dehydration of the hydroxy-ester with thionyl chloride and pyridine in the usual manner, distilled at 199-260°/4.5 mm. as a brown oil. (Found: C,

76.98; H, 6.76. $C_{18}H_{20}O_2$ requires C, 77.03; H, 6.76 per cent). The unsaturated ester on demethylation with hydriodic acid (sp. gr. 1.7) gave 4-phenyl-6-methylcoumarin, which crystallised from dilute alcohol as colourless shining needles, m.p. 131°. (Found: C, 81.43; H, 5.10. $C_{18}H_{18}O_2$ requires C, 81.36; H, 5.09 per cent).

*Preparation of 4-Phenyl-6-chlorocoumarin and 3-Methyl-4-phenyl-6-chlorocoumarin
from 2-Hydroxy-5-chlorobenzophenone*

2-Hydroxy-5-chlorobenzophenone.—The benzoate of *p*-chlorophenol (25 g.) was mixed with anhydrous aluminium chloride (26 g.) and the mixture heated in the absence of moisture at 130–40° for 1 hour. The mixture was treated with ice-cold dilute hydrochloric acid, when the product solidified on cooling. It was crystallised from dilute alcohol as yellow needles, m.p. 96–97°, yield 18 g. (Found: Cl, 15.54. $C_{13}H_9O_2Cl$ requires Cl, 15.27 per cent).

2-Methoxy-5-chlorobenzophenone was prepared from 2-hydroxy-5-chlorobenzophenone with dimethyl sulphate as usual. It was crystallised from dilute alcohol as colourless needles, m.p. 103–104°. (Found: Cl, 14.44. $C_{14}H_{11}O_2Cl$ requires Cl, 14.40 per cent).

4-Phenyl-6-chlorocoumarin.—Ethyl 2-methoxy-5-chloro- β -phenylcinnamate was prepared by the condensation of 2-methoxy-5-chlorobenzophenone with ethyl bromoacetate using zinc wool and the hydroxy-ester was dehydrated with thionyl chloride in the presence of pyridine. It distilled at 216°/2 mm. as a brown oil. (Found: Cl, 11.19. $C_{18}H_{17}O_2Cl$ requires Cl, 11.22 per cent). 4-Phenyl-6-chlorocoumarin was obtained by the demethylation of the above unsaturated ester with hydriodic acid. It crystallised from dilute alcohol as colourless needles, m.p. 156°. (Found: Cl, 13.79. $C_{15}H_9O_2Cl$ requires Cl, 13.84 per cent).

3-Methyl-4-phenyl-6-chlorocoumarin.—Ethyl 2-methoxy-5-chloro- α -methyl- β -phenylcinnamate was prepared by the condensation of 2-methoxy-5-chlorobenzophenone with ethyl α -bromopropionate in the presence of zinc wool and the subsequent dehydration of the hydroxy-ester with thionyl chloride and pyridine. It distilled at 206°/2 mm. as a brown oil. (Found: Cl, 10.69. $C_{16}H_{15}O_2Cl$ requires Cl, 10.74 per cent). On demethylation with hydriodic acid this unsaturated ester gave 3-methyl-4-phenyl-6-chlorocoumarin, which crystallised from dilute alcohol as needles, m.p. 124°. (Found: Cl, 13.11. $C_{16}H_{15}O_2Cl$ requires Cl, 13.12 per cent).

*Preparation of 4-Phenyl-6-methyl-8-chlorocoumarin and 3 : 6-Dimethyl-4-phenyl-
8-chlorocoumarin from 2-Hydroxy-3-chloro-5-methyl-benzophenone*

2-Hydroxy-3-chloro-5-methyl-benzophenone.—It was prepared from the benzoate of 2-chloro-4-methylphenol (30 g.) and anhydrous aluminium chloride (30 g.) by heating at 120–30° for 1 hour. The cooled mass was acidified with dilute hydrochloric acid, extracted with ether, the ethereal solution washed with dilute alkali solution then with water and finally dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. On removal of ether the residue was distilled at 220°, 6.5 mm. as a yellow liquid, which solidified to yellow needles, m.p. 81°, yield 20 g. (Found: Cl, 14.22. $C_{14}H_{11}O_2Cl$ requires Cl, 14.40 per cent).

2-Methoxy-3-chloro-5-methyl-benzophenone was obtained from 2-hydroxy-3-chloro-5-methyl-benzophenone by the action of dimethyl sulphate in the usual manner. It distilled at 190°/2 mm. as a thick yellow oil. (Found: Cl, 13.46. $C_{15}H_{13}O_2Cl$ requires Cl, 13.63 per cent).

4-Phenyl-6-methyl-8-chlorocoumarin.—Ethyl 2-methoxy-3-chloro-5-methyl- β -phenyl cinnamate was obtained by the condensation of 2-methoxy-3-chloro-5-methylbenzophenone and ethyl bromoacetate using zinc wool and the subsequent dehydration of the hydroxy-ester with thionyl chloride and pyridine in the usual manner. It distilled at 215°/2 mm. as a brown viscous oil. (Found: Cl, 10.70. $C_{19}H_{19}O_3Cl$ requires Cl, 10.74 per cent). This unsaturated ester on demethylation with hydriodic acid gave 4-phenyl-6-methyl-8-chlorocoumarin, which crystallised from dilute alcohol as colourless light needles, m.p. 152-53°. (Found: Cl, 13.15. $C_{16}H_{11}O_2$ Cl requires Cl, 13.12 per cent).

3:6-Dimethyl-4-phenyl-8-chlorocoumarin.—Ethyl 2-methoxy-3-chloro- α :5-dimethyl- β -phenylcinnamate was prepared by the reaction of 2-methoxy-3-chloro-5-methylbenzophenone with ethyl α -bromo-propionate in the presence of zinc wool and the hydroxy-ester was dehydrated with thionyl chloride and pyridine. It crystallised from ether as colourless needles, m.p. 120°. (Found: Cl, 10.33. $C_{20}H_{21}O_3Cl$ requires Cl, 10.30 per cent). The unsaturated ester was demethylated with hydriodic acid to give 3:6-dimethyl-4-phenyl-8-chlorocoumarin. It crystallised from dilute alcohol as colourless needles, m.p. 172°. (Found: Cl, 12.42. $C_{17}H_{13}O_2$ Cl requires Cl, 12.48 per cent).

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